

Structural and optical band gap analysis of Mo-modified PbTiO₃ ceramics

Pragyanand Prajapati and Akhilesh Kumar Singh*

School of Materials Science and Technology Indian Institute of Technology(Banaras Hindu University)

Varanasi 221005 Utter Pradesh,India.

aksingh_mst@itbhu.ac.in, 9415619018

Abstract

Perovskite oxides have been recently supposed to be attractive class of materials for use in photovoltaic devices to harvest light energy with various functional properties(1). The spontaneous polarization in ferroelectric perovskite oxides promotes the desirable separation of photo-excited carriers (1). Modoping restricts the recombination rate by charge transfer mechanism promising better optical performance (2). In this attempt Pb(Mo_xTi_{1-x})O₃ (x= 0.03 ,0.05 and 0.10) ceramics were synthesized by solid state route. Rietveld refinement of x-ray diffraction patterns reveals that Pb(Mo_xTi_{1-x})O₃ crystalize into single phase tetragonal structure with space group P4mm. UV-vis spectroscopy measurements shows low band gap between conduction and valence band suitable for electron transfer under illumination.

Keywords: X-ray diffraction, Rietveld refinement, UV-Visible spectroscopy, FullProf suite and SEM-EDS.

References

1. I. Grinberg et al, Nature **503**(2013)509.
2. T. Pham, S. G. Kang and E. W. Shin, Applied surface science **411**(2017) 18.